

Studies on the Changes in DTPA-extractable Micronutrients (Fe, Mn & Cu) in Soils following Incubation and Plant Uptake

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The DTPA-extractable iron, manganese and copper status of three alluvial soils and their change in amount on equilibration for a period of seven days at moisture-saturation and subsequently after growing soybean plants on those soils for a period of one month have been studied. The amount of iron, manganese and copper was increased in all the three soils after seven days of incubation from which it can be concluded that the mobilization of the micronutrients in soils was increased on incubation under moisture-saturated condition. After growing crop for a period of one month under similar conditions amount of the micronutrients again came down almost to the original levels. The apparent decrease in availability of those micronutrient elements is obviously due to plant uptake and partially due to microbial consumption and refixation in soil.

THE role of micronutrients in plant nutrition has become firmly established both in agricultural sciences and in broad-scale agricultural practices. Although most arable soils are well supplied with micronutrients the problem of deficiency has cropped up with the intensive cultivation and various chemical fertilizers such as phosphate application practices followed in recent years. Besides, it is not the total amount but the available quantity of any micronutrient which is important in deciding the actual uptake by a particular plant under any particular soil condition. As the ultimate source of micronutrients is the soil, it is necessary to know the available micronutrient status of a soil. Among the various methods employed for the determination of available status of micronutrients like copper, iron and manganese, the DTPA (Diethylene triamine penta acetic acid)-extraction developed by Lindsay & Norvell¹ has been found to best correlate with the plant uptake. Although Lopez and Graham² later used a modified DTPA-extractant to determine the labile pool of Zn, Fe, Mn and Cu in soil at different pH values, the former method is still considered to be extremely useful for monitoring the availability of those cations in soil.

In the present investigation, the changes in DTPA-extractable micronutrients (Fe, Mn, & Cu) in three alluvial soils on incubation for one week under moisture saturated condition have been studied. Changes in available micronutrient status of the same soils, after growing soybean plants on them for a period of one month, have also been investigated.

Experimental :

Three soils used in the present investigation were obtained from the State Livestock Farm, Kalyani (K-soil), the Viswa Vidyalaya Teaching

Farm, Mandowri (M-soil) and from the village of Chakdah (C-soil) respectively—all belonging to the district of Nadia, West Bengal. The fields from which the upper 23 cm layer of the soils were collected are under the programme of intensive cultivation. All the soils are light, medium-textured and belong to the comparatively recent Gangetic alluvium which show no sharp profile development. The soils were air-dried, ground and sieved through a 0.2 mm sieve. Some physico-chemical properties of the soils necessary for an understanding of the results of the present experiment are shown in Table 1.

TABLE—1
PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOIL SAMPLES.

Sl. No. of Expt.	Property	Results of analysis		
		K-soil	C-soil	M-soil
1.	Saturation Percentage (%)	5.6	4.4	4.8
2.	Soil pH (1 : 2.5 soil water ratio)	8.2	8.4	7.7
3.	Available P ₂ O ₅ (ppm)	40.0	24.5	18.0
4.	Nitrogen (%)	0.09	0.08	0.06
5.	Organic Carbon (%)	0.64	0.61	0.45
6.	C : N ratio	7.21 : 1	8.08 : 1	7.65 : 1
7.	CEC (me/100 gm)	44.0	31.7	18.5
8.	Total Free oxides of Iron (Fe ₂ O ₃ %)	0.95	1.51	1.35

Procedure : 800 gms of each soil were taken in plastic pots which were coated externally with coal-tar and the soil inside was maintained at moisture-saturated condition by applying appropriate amount of de-ionized water. The pots including three replications for each soil sample, were kept at room temperature and after seven days of incubation 10.0 gms of soil were sampled out from each pot with the help of a spoon-headed spatula for subsequent extraction of the micronutrient elements. Afterwards, in each pot five seeds of soybean (*Glycine max* Merr.) were sown and t

moisture status of the soils in the pots were maintained at saturated condition as before by adding requisite quantity of water. The seeds were previously germinated in a growth chamber and washed thoroughly with de-ionized water. A control series with the usual replications were also simultaneously run.

After one month the plants were taken away from the pots, roots were carefully eliminated and the contents of the pot were thoroughly mixed. Subsequently, 10.0 gms of this soil (on dry-weight basis) were taken and analyzed for DTPA-extractable iron, manganese and copper.

Fig. 1 (a, b, c) Changes in DTPA-Extractable Fe, Mn & Cu in Soil on Incubation.

Extraction : The soil (10.0 gms) was shaken with 20 ml of the DTPA-extractant solution for 2 hours and filtered. The DTPA-triethanolamine extractant was prepared in the same manner as proposed by Lindsay and Norvell¹. To the filtrate 3 ml of concentrated nitric acid and 5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid were added and the resulting solution was digested on a hot plate. The digestion procedure was repeated with another 2 ml of concentrated nitric acid until all the organic matter and the metal-DTPA chelates were completely decomposed. The resulting material was taken with redistilled water and the volume was made upto the mark in a 50 ml volumetric flask. Appropriate aliquots were taken from this solution for the estimation of iron, manganese and copper by the usual colorimetric methods as outlined below.

Estimation of iron : Iron has been determined by reduction of ferric iron to the ferrous state with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and subsequent formation of an intense red ferrous chelate with ortho-phenanthroline as described by Snell and Snell² and also cited by Jackson⁴.

Estimation of manganese : Manganese was estimated colorimetrically by the periodate method developed by Willard and Greathouse⁵. It is based upon the oxidation of all manganese species at lower oxidation states to MnO_4^- by potassium metaperiodate in a strongly acid solution.

Estimation of Copper : Copper was estimated colorimetrically by the method of Cheng and Bray⁶. In this method a mixture of citrate and EDTA was used as masking agents for most of the interfering ions without preventing formation of the complex between copper and diethyldithiocarbamate. The Copper-complex was extracted by redistilled carbon tetrachloride and then measured colorimetrically.

A Spectronic-20 (Bausch & Lomb) spectrophotometer was used for all absorbance measurements.

All the reagents and chemicals used were of A.R. quality.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data for DTPA-extractable micronutrients under present investigation are given in Table 2. The table contains the values for both air-dried original soil samples and the incubated ones.

It is evident from the results that the amount of DTPA-extractable iron increased in all the three soils after seven days of incubation under moisture-saturated condition. The values decreased nearly to the original level after growing soybean plants on those soils for a period of one month.

The DTPA-extractable manganese content of all the soils were found to increase considerably on incubation, but after growing soybean for one month the corresponding amounts were found to be greater than the original ones in both K-soil and M-soil. In case of C-soil however, the DTPA-extractable manganese was decreased to a level much lower than that of the original values.

A slight increase in DTPA-extractable copper was found in all the three soils after seven days of incubation. After growing the crop for one month on those soils it was reduced to much lower values in case of C-soil and M-soil but almost to the same values in K-soil.

The changes in DTPA-extractable iron, manganese and copper are also shown graphically in Figs. 1. (a, b, c). From Table 2 and from the figures it is clear that there is increase in mobilization of all the three micronutrients in soil on incubation under moisture-saturated condition. Venkata Subrahmanyam and Mehta⁷ also observed that availabilities of iron and manganese in soil increase considerably under such a condition. On prolonged incubation, however, no further increase in available status of the above micronutrients was obtained. On the contrary, a slight decreasing trend was

TABLE—2
CHANGES IN THE AMOUNT OF DTPA-EXTRACTABLE Fe, Mn AND Cu

	K-Soil			C-Soil			M-Soil		
	Air-Dry Soil	After 7 days of incubation	After one month of crop grown	Air-Dry Soil	After 7 days of incubation	After one month of crop grown	Air-Dry Soil	After 7 days of incubation	After one month of crop grown
Fe (ppm)*	18.13	42.50	20.63 (39.65)**	15.63	31.25	20.00 (30.80)	31.25	36.25	32.50 (36.04)
Mn (ppm)*	7.50	59.38	11.25 (54.50)	15.02	26.75	3.75 (24.65)	11.25	55.00	15.63 (53.35)
Cu (ppm)*	2.75	6.50	2.88 (6.40)	5.02	6.50	2.50 (6.42)	4.25	5.75	3.88 (5.70)

* The values given are mean of three replications.

** Figures in parenthesis denote the corresponding values of the control.

noticed in all cases as is indicated by the dotted portion of the curves in the figures. This is obviously due to any possible microbial consumption and re-fixation of the elements in soil.

As regards rate of mobilization, among the three soils K-soil seems to be more susceptible to moisture treatment. On incubation under moisture-saturated condition the K-soil shows about a 2.5-fold increase in available iron and 7.5-fold increase in available manganese. The rate of increase of available copper is also highest in this soil in comparison with the other two soils. The reason for this higher rate of microcutrient mobilization in the K-soil may be attributed to the higher organic matter content and the resulting instant lowering of pH or more intense reducing environment set up under such circumstances. That lowering of pH through the influence of adequate moisture causes an increase in availability of a micronutrient like manganese is also evident from the observation of Hossner and Blanchar^a.

On growing plants for a period of one month a slight overall increase in DTPA-extractable micronutrient elements is expected in all the three soils, obviously due to mobilization of those elements from the so-called non-labile or semi-labile pool through the influence of root interception whereby some organic chelating agents are produced which tend to hold more micronutrients in solution. An apparent decrease in the amount of available micronutrients in soil after growing plants on them

is supposed to be mainly due to plant uptake or crop removal as well as in part, due to fixation in soil in course of prolonged incubation. In case of K-soil the decrease in available micronutrient status is quite conspicuous. Narrower C : N ratio coupled with high available P₂O₅-content of the K-soil may be responsible for the above decrease in available micronutrient status through microbial consumption or chemical fixation.

Further studies on the actual plant uptake of the micronutrients during various stages of the growth period involving plant tissue or dry matter analysis are in progress.

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